

STRIPPING SURGERY FOR VARICOSE VEINS

It is a type of [vein treatment near me](#) that is used to remove varicose veins from the thighs and legs. These are twisted and puffy veins that you can see under the skin. They have a bluish, purple, and red color. They generally develop in the legs but they can also appear in other parts of the body.

When the vein valves aren't functioning properly then varicose veins form in the legs. In veins, there is only a one-way valve that prevents the blood from flowing back into the heart. Rather than continuing to the heart, the blood begins to collect in the vein, when these valves don't work properly. This resulting in swollen and painful veins.

Varicose vein stripping is a kind of **varicose vein treatment** that prevents them from coming back. This process is also known as vein stripping with ablation, ligation, and avulsion.

Risk factors associated with varicose veins stripping

This procedure of varicose vein stripping is low risk and safe. There are some risks associated with varicose vein stripping surgery are:

- Scarring or bruising
- Injury to nerve
- Allergy to anesthesia
- Heavily bleeding
- Formation of blood clots

According to a **vein specialist**, these risks are rare. This procedure isn't recommended for:

A person who has poor leg circulation

A person with skin infections

A person who has a blood clotting issue

Overweighted person

For pregnant women

Why is stripping surgery get done?

A **vein doctor** may recommend varicose veins stripping if you are experiencing these symptoms:

1. Ulcers and skin sores
2. Throbbing, constant pain in the legs
3. Veins started bleeding out
4. Formation of blood clots

If you are concerned about the cosmetic appearance of your legs then also you can go for varicose vein stripping surgery. Speak with **vein doctor la jolla** and he/she will tell you that it is a better option for you or not.

How should you prepare for this?

Before the procedure, your [vein specialist la jolla](#) will perform a physical examination. It's important that you must tell your doctor about any medication that you are taking. Some of the medication will cause bleeding during vein stripping, so your doctor asks you to stop this medication.

To get a better view of the valves and veins your doctor may use a handheld ultrasound device. To get the best image results of affected veins they may also order a duplex scan. If you may have blood clots in the veins then in this test they can be easily visible. This will help your doctor to see these varicose veins in more detail.

What can you expect during stripping surgery of varicose veins?

You may receive either spinal or general anesthesia before the procedure depending on your **varicose vein treatment la jolla**. If you take general anesthesia, then throughout the procedure you will be asleep. You will stay awake during the whole procedure after taking the spinal anesthesia as it numbs only your lower body. Near the bottom and top of your damaged vein, your surgeon will make small cuts or incisions.